

The Main Means Of Converting the Phrase Free Unit Idioms (Comparison, Hyperbole, Metaphor)

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Abstract

The wording includes all short term, strong and beautiful, with a figurative sense, which is formed with time in the mouth of people who were followed from generation to generation and are polished with care, craftsmanship, and taste.

Albanian is one of the Indo-European languages very rich in phraseology. Creating and using them shows its unlimited opportunities to meet with its means of communication functions and enables the company to the demand of the growing development of the semantic lexical unit.

Ways of implementing the movement of meaning to the converting from free units to phraseological ones are comparison, metaphor, hyperbole, and litota. But, by weight, by volume and the quality of implementation, the first place occupies the metaphor, after that is the comparison, litota and at the end is hyperbole. Hyperbole is often seen as a kind of comparison, we have shared as a special tool, and it forms the subgroup that appears with its distinctive features from other groups.

Keywords: *phraseology, Short term, artistry, taste, metaphors, comparisons, hyperbole, litota,*

Introduction

The wording is a broad field of study that has occupied an important place in our linguistic studies. In today situation we can talk about mature studies in this area that cover all aspects and, even, which have led to the emergence of the Phraseology of Albanian Language as an independent science. However, as everywhere, even here, there is no way you were treated to exhaustible or requiring more extensive explanations of the most illustrative. This has been the impetus that we in this paper, as far as space allows us to do his subject some figurative transformation tools of a free unit to idiomatic one (comparison, hyperbole, metaphor).Linguistic phraseology is a huge treasure of very valuable heritage of oral creativity of the people. As a broad field of study and linguistics, Albanian estimable achievement marked the main directions:

a. In the direct study, viewing it on all sides: on the semantic, and structural functions; dozens of studies have been made of genuine monographic works. Today, studies of Albanian Language phraseology created a general scientific view, which becomes indicative of what Prof. Jani Thomai underlined that "it can be said that it (meaning phraseology) is formed as a linguistic discipline, object, timber with its methods."(1)

b. This treasure is reflected in various Albanian dictionaries such as Explanatory Dictionary; in a Proper Phraseological Dictionary (very voluminous), but also in the dictionary two or more languages and many Dialectal Dictionaries. We could even say that in the Albanian - Latin Dictionary of Frang Bardhi (1635) reflected some idioms units. They are not lacking in the Greek-Albanian Dictionary of Kostandin Kristoforidhi (1904) but is widely find at New Vocabulary (rare words used in northern Albania) of Nikola Gazuli (1942/2005), we find as the main course at New Dictionary of Pano Tase.(1942). After the country's liberation from fascist invaders, work to collect, study and lexicographical presentation were organized and planned in the proper scientific basis. Studies have also, in this period of the Explanatory Albanian Dictionaries compiled, together with the word, reflected the phraseology. Most comprehensive and most fulfill the Today Albanian Language Dictionary (1980), but without setting aside the Albanian Language Dictionary (1954/2005), as the Today Albanian Dictionary (1984/2002). In 1999 marked the greatest achievement of Latin phraseologies. Researcher Jani Thomai published Phraseological Albanian Language Dictionary, a work of quality, volume, but equipped with a preface study, which is in the true sense of the word, a work of genuine science, which reflects the contemporary concepts of phraseology. Not to mention the Phraseological Dictionary of borrowed units of Ali Jashari, Phraseological Balkan Dictionary (5 languages) with a group of authors of the dictionary of

others, as well as over 20 Dialectical Dictionaries, that the case involving contributing itself to the presentation and preserving this nationwide treasure.

The wording includes all short term, strong and beautiful, with a figurative sense, which is formed with time in the mouth of people who were followed from generation to generation and are polished with care, craftsmanship, and taste. Jani Thomai admits that " idioms unit is a unit of linguistic meaning of autonomous, consisting of two or more words scoring, with members of building sustainable, formed historically for a long time, that has the value of a single word, reproduced in the discourse as ready and functions as an indivisible unit. "(2)

Albanian is an Indo-European language very rich phraseology. Creating and using them shows its unlimited opportunities to meet with its means of communication functions and enables the company to the demand of the growing development of the semantic lexical units. The phraseology is an essential part of the vocabulary in different situations discourse. Possession its competence and capability display the user, but when it is used with ingenuity and craftsmanship makes this speech more expressive, more functional and more prominent. Idioms units, more than other elements of outside language in communication, connect us directly with the ethnography of speaking, more pleasant. They exhibit strong stylistic values , and they are characteristic of all discourse and functional styles of Albanian. (3)

Most prominent here are casual and conversational discourse. The wording of the Albanian language has emphasized popular character. Slang folk or a variety of speech popular is rich with such units. (4)

In general, the spoken language is rich with phraseology and an essential part of their being absorbed strongly from the written language and is standardized more soon. Many of them are built with words that mark the things, objects, animals, birds, plants, parts of the human body, etc., that are directly related to human life and the environment in which the Albanian appear materially, mentally, spiritually or esthetically.

Modeling of idioms units

Idioms units are equivalent to the word. It separate as a unit of lexical structure of Albanian Language with three distinctive features, such as the constituent members (from source is usually phrase); lexical thorough and independent meaning (like the word) and grammatical meanings (shown through different syntactic functions). As word units mark spiritual and concrete idioms, the occurrence of various phenomena of the world around us, marking the actions, features, circumstances, etc.

Prof. Jani Thomai admits that "in the phraseology has types and models, although they are specific and conventional. This means, also, that there are classifical criteria, such as semantic, structural, functional criteria, etc.. This does not mean that in phraseology has the regular, systematic backgrounds as same as the words. On the contrary, in phraseology types, patterns, classes, groups created by affinity or by equality (formal, semantic, functional, etc.) of units formed independently. Regardless of the difficulties that represent modulations, this author received them for idioms units. Idioms units that are created using a comparison, hyperbole, and metaphor, as well as other units, despite the multiplicity of values, first, there are lexical units as scoring (branding), that is, they are nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs.

Nominative-units (equivalent to a noun), such as: "*Slice on the tail*"; "*Chump on the saddle*"; "*Non licked veal*"; "*Bag with fleas*," etc.

Adjectival-units (equivalent to an adjective), such as: "*With a merry heart*" (delighted) happy; "*With wide soul*"; "*With frozen blood*"; "*With injured heart*," etc.

Verbal-units (equivalent to a verb, usually here introduced the verb units "*become*"), such as: "*It became coal*" is (something) was burned completely; "*It became smoke*" is (someone), "*Disappeared*"; "*Immediately fled*"; "*Escaped quickly*", etc.

Adverbial-units (equivalent to an adverb; here usually included a comparison of hyperbole units) such as: "*as father and son are alike*"; "*They are very like each other*" (for two people); "*With naked sword*"; etc.

Structural Modeling

According to Structural modeling idioms units are shared:

Units with phrase structure, such as: "*It makes pod*"; "*He became bone and skin*"; "*It became soot*", etc.

Units with sentence structure, such as: "*If the donkey ate bread (one)*," etc.

Modeling by lexical and grammatical nature of limbs

We distinguish variety of building structures, such as: *noun + noun*; *noun + adjective*; *verb + noun*; *adjective + noun + noun*; *conjunction + noun + noun*, etc..

Syntax modeling

There are a lot of varieties in syntactic relations that put members of the phraseology with each other. Relationships encounter between words in the Albanian language, also carried the phraseology. Therefore, we are presenting some of the most important:

The determinant relationship, such as: "*As killed snake*," "*As owl swamps*," etc.

The objective relationship, such as; "*It makes the fly (flea) buffalo*"; "*It closed the door*," etc. The circumstantial relationship, such as: "*It sent behind the sun (someone)*"; "*Behind the world*," etc.

Figures of idioms units

In many idioms units, we see not only their historical development, but the scale of this development in the Albanian language, but also in many other Indo-European languages (as in Italian, French, Greek, Russian, Rumanian, etc.) It is accepted, and it is argued that the idioms unit is formed by figurative conversion of a free phrase (in this kind of phrase about the connection of the free phrase / stable phrase). During of this development (which is a long historical process) among others we could mention: partial or full morphological petrify of the limbs of free phrase; meaning petrify; meaning and remeaning of the phrase limbs, (which now becomes a scoring independent unit, as well as word), performing syntactic different functions, striking emotional coloring, semantic developments of word - formation, etc.

In our paper, we will focus particularly on the implementation of this movement to realize the figuring especially at the process that based on the movement of comparison, metaphor, and hyperbole. Thus, we turn to semantic motivation and the level of motivation. Prof.Jani Thomai, one of the researchers of Albanian Language, which was taken directly to its wording (with authenticated works with a Theoretical Dictionary that is highly valued by the linguistic environment, states that the motivation of the unit helps the discovery of idioms; one of the members of the idioms units can bear the brunt of grammatical, semantic, idiomatic, motional style or word formation. According to this author, whom we rely extensively on paper, we can ask five hearths, which should not necessarily be to ask each member of phraseological units, because the limb cannot be the carrier of all these spots, but in many cases, one limb can carry the value of two or three spots. The hearths may be:

1. Grammatical hearth, which determines the value of the unit lexicon and grammatical idioms arose;
2. Meaning hearth, which defines the lexical meaning of unit; This center is the most important limb to determine and to identify the semantic motivation of this unit;
3. Hearth idiomatic, which means a limb with very dark sense and with a hardened outer form
4. Stylistic emotional center, which bears the brunt for the stylistic emotional coloring of all idioms unit (the colouring is inseparable component of phraseology);
5. The hearth of word formation that is the topic word-forming units (compound words) created and which are mostly equivalent to semantically. According to the above five spots, which easily accepted as classification criteria to determine the motivation of idioms units, units that we've got to analyze, divided into two major groups:
 - a. motivation phraseological units, i.e. the unit to which idioms can get the kind of movement meaning, the way, and means of implementation;

b. Dismotivation phraseological units, which in its present state (i.e. in the field synchronous) are intractable semantically or their breakdown presents many difficulties.

c. Treatments and contemplation by the group we have met repeatedly, and in our work will focus on an overview of the new idioms units in Albanian, in what means the most important as (comparison, metaphor, and hyperbole) in the process of idioms unit creation.

The manner of expression is an intellectual trend of every person and especially this appears to cultural people, with an estimable heritage and language with a high degree of processing in all subsystems, particularly in the lexical and stylistic system.

The Albanian language is recognized as polysemantic that is in her many words (about 60% of lexicon) have more than one meaning. Abstraction and using of figures are phenomena and processes in creating makrosystems of these words or in the so-called *internal movement of meaning*.

It is a strong phenomenon in the communicative syntagmatic, in the turning of figures not only the words but also the notions of more than one branding limb, so gradual from idioms units to the triggering unit, therefore, from the casual construction they return to paradigmatic units where the unit hasn't already become an object of study of syntax, but lexicology and lexical semantics. Examples of concrete tools of conversion of free idioms unit into phrase units we have received from the Phraseological Albanian Language Dictionary of Prof. Jani Thomai.

Figurative units established by comparison idioms

The vocabulary of a language rich in several ways: by creating new words and new meanings or by borrowings from different languages. Enrichment through word formation can be done with words and idioms units. The words are created in various ways. According to Albanian origin, they can be related forms, composition, with adherence, with a conjunction before the word and change of lexicon and grammatical category. But phraseological units created through very long discourse uses the notions of relevant phrases or sentence. Discourse, particularly that of casual and it conversational, as well as the functional style of the Albanian language, made environments powerful and indispensable for shaping units idioms, either numerically because the Albanian language compared with other languages is very rich in such units. Greek language, for example, one of the oldest Indo-European languages and with a much higher degree of processing has not yet her phraseological dictionary, but also the theoretical and lexico-semantic studies aren't at the same level with the languages of Russia, English, etc.), even qualitatively. Even ambiguity in communication is a very prominent feature of Albanian speakers. Frequency comparisons of persons, actions, objects, events, etc., are present in every discursive environment.

The comparison is one of three ways that we are taking into consideration for the figurative turning of free phrase (a Syntagma has at least two branding limbs). But, the *comparison* itself, presupposes the process, but also the image that implements this process. Prof. Jani Thomai when dealing artistry characterizations in Albanian, says the comparison is on the main road and rich characterizations. The comparison, as we know, it is also a literary figure. In the vocabulary of today's Albanian language, he defined "figure of speech that is used to make a living more clearly expressed an opinion, pointing at something less familiar to anything similar to the more familiar, more clearly the most meaningful, such as: "**white as snow** ." (5)

But we are not in the field of literature and not analyze a literary work of its figuration. Indeed fiction is the laboratory creation of hundreds and thousands of new words, the conception of meaning, especially figurative ones, we are in linguistics, in lexicology and more are in lexicography, where the lexical unit is structural, semantically and grammatically self-sustaining. Moreover, when it comes to idioms units, which among other things should appear as branding unit with nominal, adjectival, verbal and adverbial value. In everyday speech, we face in discursive situation varied in countless speakers in hundreds of uses comparison. But not everyone associated with these uses is phraseology or idioms construction. Prof. Jani Thomai rightly stopped in defining the boundaries of a linguistic unit with its figurative use, what becomes the indicator displayed stylistics

language from literary stylistics. He highlights that "the use of symbolic speech is a tool of literary stylistics, known for thrilling pronounced colouring there is widespread in the speakers of the language and is not binding on all, sometimes it is the creation of an author and often remains with his work" It is easily understandable that so far we are talking about a figurative use of the word or words with figurative meanings in addition to understanding the literal meaning. With idioms units are different, the phenomenon is much more complicated here. For idioms unit, first emerged as branding unit (scoring) not simple, but with a particular set of functional and semantic relations. Specific is such that a unit does not arise as a direct marker of the item, the feature, the action of the circumstance, etc., but as **mediated triggering** "symbolic" through a linguistic feature. This metaphorical essential (the metaphorical word here taken as a term inclusive movement of meaning and branding, when the center of this movement is a linguistic feature) of the phraseological meaning brings that type of meaning to figurative, and it should be kept in mind during the explanation in a dictionary. And in the *Phraseological Albanian Language Vocabulary* of Jani Thomai (1999), we have found dozens of idioms constructed units compared with conjunctions such as **like / but / as**.

a. Phraseological units with a conjunction as: "*save as my eyes*"; "*left as a shepherd without cattle*"; "*as cat and mouse*," etc.

b. Phraseological units with a conjunction like: In situations discourse different or by selecting individual tools eloquent of speakers we face constructions even as: "*like lambs to the slaughter*" "*as thunder in the blue sky*."

c. Phraseological units with a conjunction like if:

There are a small number of units with this conjunction, which are with the structure of the sentence and tend more to manner sentences than to comparative ones, such as: "*stay as the ass ate the bread*"(for a person that is too sad), etc.

Motivational limbs of comparison

One of the most interesting phenomena in return for a free phrase tracing the ethnic idioms preferential limb that serve as a basis for comparison, a motivational theme that appears in the newly created entity conception or the birth of figurative things. The majority parts of local idioms that we received for review in this paper are a popular source, are creations of the people and hence have entered to normative vocabulary. Rarer are those belonging to the intellectual world of the very few units are borrowed, such as: "*like the sword of Demokleu*", etc. Our people with intelligence, with sharpness and versatility that characterizes, found in the surrounding world and especially from the animal world (without excluding the real property that proprietary spirits) animals, birds, insects that have quality, physical features, size of striking a slightly distinct functions and easily build (motivate) a consistent comparison. This comparison, two or more limbs, being used for a long time and by many speakers, earns state (status) of an independent unit to positive or negative very large cargo exciting. Relying on this point of view, we are enabled to do again repackaging of reclassification:

a. The group of phraseological units that comes from an anecdote which is based **on an animal** p.sh : "*It went like lambs to the slaughter*"; "*It suits like a donkey saddle*," etc.

b. The group of phraseological units that comes from a comparison of **the animals**, which have a physical feature or dimension that flashy, such as: *as a goat among the sheep*, etc.

c. The group of phraseological units motivated by a comparison of **the animals** that exhibit qualities in a relationship with other animals. Included are: "*cat and mouse*," "*the fox looks like a chicken*", etc.

- d.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a comparison of **the proprietary world**, such as: "*It stands like a fence pole,*" etc.
- e.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a comparison of **the human world**, especially the pastoral, such as: "*like a shepherd without cattle,*" etc.
- f.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a comparison from **the world of birds**, such as: "*as the birds of the Raven*"; "*as the Albanian birds*"; "*like crows after carrion,*" etc.
- g.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a comparison from **the world of** of reptiles, such as: "*It lifts (serving) as a serpent under the stone*"; "*He is like flies to honey,*" etc.
- h.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a comparison of **the plant world**: "*She is like May flowers*"; "*It sits as in (on) thorns,*" etc.

Phraseological units created by metaphorical idioms

The metaphor is the main tool for the creation of local idioms and metaphors is a manufacturing process. There are thousands and thousands of units formed in Albanian (and not only in that language) through it. Prof. Jani Thomai says that "in the field of Albanian as the unit features are familiar idioms: neutralizing internal reports syntax, one value with the meaning of the word categorical and functional in discourse."

The figures are inextricably linked with metaphor. As we said the comparison characterized by a idioms unit essentially metaphorical.

Birth of a unit idioms through metaphorical is a process at least with four steps: cheap phrase - compared - metaphor (which refers to the process of the collapse of vibrating comparative) - unit idioms (the birth of a new lexical unit with all values and functions that the equivalent of her, word).

Kosovo researcher Zenun Goxhaj said that metaphorical phraseology and phraseological metaphor are fusion, are semantic and stylistic elements. Metaphors in the foreground figure stylistic issue, then, the unity of semantic faded. At idioms units, semantic unity is the basic features ". (6)

In the Dictionary of Albanian Language (1999) of Prof. Jani Thomai, but also in the explanatory dictionaries to all of them Albanian dialect, idioms find many units that are created by metaphor, creating a lexicon-semantic field assessable by the number of units, including but values for scoring, exciting, stylistic, word formation, etc., in this group paradigmatic units, we may require more than anywhere categories and the types, what is an imperative in today semantic studies. Suffice it to mention only word formation phraseology metaphorically ability to assert this phenomenon scientifically. So in the Albanian Language, we find, for example: *with heart burst - heartbroken*, etc. The metaphor of semantic abstraction here resizing, language and show their intelektual potentials, regardless of the source of idioms units directly from the fountain is popular.

Motivational limbs of metaphor

As the motivated units with the comparison, even here, one of the phenomena most interesting during the return of a phrase of free idioms unit tracing the affiliation preferential limb that serves as the basis for metaphor, which appears as a topic inspiring conception the newly created unit or figurative birth.

In this paradigmatic group, the majority of units are sourced popular idioms, are creations of the people and hence have entered normative vocabulary. Relying on this point of view, we again try to do repackaging of reclassification:

- a.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a metaphor that relates to animals has a physical or dimension feature that flashy, such as: "*The bear of the mountain*", "*The black sheep*", "*The alarm pig*," etc.
- b.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a metaphor from proprietary world, such as: "*It became wax*," etc.
- c.** The group of phraseological units motivated by a metaphor of the human world, especially the pastoral, such as: "*With filled spirit*," "*With little spirit*", etc.

- d. The group of phraseological units motivated by a metaphor from the world of birds, such as: "*It became whistle*," "*It is a bird without feathers*," etc.
- e. The group of phraseological units motivated by a metaphor from the world of insects, such as: "*It made beehives*," "*It made flee*," etc.
- f. The group of phraseological units motivated by a metaphor from the vegetable, such as: "*It became bur to me*," etc.

The figures of idioms units generated with hyperbole

Hyperbole is another important tool for which the motivation of many local idioms. But, in different works, regardless of the size or the problems that are treated, this means almost overlooked. It is mentioned here and there, but compared to other tools by which achieved meaning in Albanian movement, as a comparison, metaphor, analogy, euphemisms, etc., leaves much to be desired. In Today Albanian Language Dictionary for hyperbole is this definition: " It is a literary figure of speech that is built by increasing excessively beings, objects, phenomena, properties, etc. (7)

By definition, excludes the notion of linguistic hyperbole. Often this literary figure, but also as a tool in our case for the realization of movement of units of meaning and idioms conception, it is seen either opposed or in comparison.

But concrete material with which we take very subject has given us to break out the comparison, since the turn of a hyperbolic metaphor, etc. In literary literature, the hyperbole is directly related first with litota (accepted as the opposite of hyperbole, or reduction of objects, phenomena, actions, features, etc.). Although the hyperbole does not include litota, the performance of tradition we are and how we recover phenomenon parameter that organizes a small group of units idioms.

a. The group of phraseological units derived with hyperbole. We provide a heterogeneous group, within which, as well as the groups of comparison and metaphor; we can split the subdivision according to the structure, semantic relations (synonyms, polisemi, antonimi, etc.), motivation, as notional and of preferential appropriation of the limb that appears as hyperbole, etc. But we don't do consciously to avoid falling into repetition, such as:

"The whole world, (all people)"; "*It makes the fly bull*"; "*He has a sea heart*"; "*she has a face seven hectare*," etc.

b. The group of phraseological units realized with litota, such as: "*He has two-plyrib (someone is very frail)*"; "*It barely held up*"; "*It is skinny*"; "*It takes blood to eyebrow*"; "*It became acorn*"; "*It became a punch*"; "*It became messy*", etc.

Motivational limb of hyperbole

The diversity of motivations in this group is great paradigmatic, although conditioned by the spirit, items, objects, phenomena, etc. The important thing here is that the creative ability of Albanian speaker created one such unit.

a. The group of phraseological units realized with motivated by a hyperbole / litota related to animals, such as: "*It makes ox with calf*," etc.

b. Group units idioms motivated by a hyperbole / litota from the proprietary world, such as: "*It makes hair to beam*"; "*I see behind the mountain*," etc.

c. The group of phraseological units motivated by a hyperbole / litota from the human world, such as: "*She enters Satan into the bottle*"; "*It makes the priest pregnant*," etc.

d. The group of phraseological units motivated by a hyperbole / litota from the world of bird, such as *It is a cock with goods*", etc.

e. The group of phraseological units motivated by a hyperbole / litota from the world of insects, such as: "*It makes fly to Buffalo*", "*It became roach*", etc.

k. The group of phraseological units motivated by a hyperbole / litota from the plant world, such as: "*The oak without branch*"; "*The oak with deep roots*," etc.

In conclusion, we can say that the movement of ways to accomplish a transformation of meaning from free phrase to phraseological one are: the comparison, the metaphor, the litota and the hyperbole. But, by weight, by volume and the quality of implementation, the first place occupies the metaphor, the second place occupies comparison, the third one occupies hyperbole, and the fourth one is litota. Hyperbole is often seen as a kind of comparison, but we share a special tool, and it forms the subgroup that appears with its distinctive features from other groups.

Bibliographical references

1. Thomai, J., "*Phraseological Dictionary of Albanian Language*," Tirana, 1999, p.34;
2. Thomas, J., "*Albanian Language Lexicology*," Tirana, 1999, f.210;
3. Lloshi, J., "*Stylistics and pragmatics*," Tirana 1999;
4. Shkurtaj, W., "*Sociolinguistics*," Tirana, 1996, f.106;
5. "*Today Albanian Language Dictionary*," Tirana, 1980, f.887;
6. Gjocaj, Z., "*Stylistic Semantic Lexicon Structure of Latin phraseology*," Pristina, 2001 f.259;
7. "*Phraseological Dictionary of Albanian Language*," Tirana 1980;
8. Memushaj, R., "*Introduction to Linguistics*," Tirana, 2004;
9. Memisha, V., "*Occurrence during the formation of partial semantic adjectives in Albania*," Gjirokastra, 1999;
10. Zhenet, Zh., "*Figures*," Prishtina, 1985;
11. Thomas, J., "*The Issues of phraseology in Albania*," Tirana, 1981;
12. Shkurtaj, W., "*Ethnography of speaking in Albania*," Tirana, 2004;